

Incidence of rice tungro bacilliform (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) on susceptible rice cultivars

P. Q. Cabauatan and H. Hibino, Plant Pathology Department, IRRI

Tungro is caused by RTBV and RTSV. Greenhouse and laboratory experiments have shown that the green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* Distant vector transmits either both viruses together, or RTBV or RTSV alone from plants infected with both viruses. Plants infected with both viruses have severe symptoms; those infected with RTBV have mild symptoms, and those with RTSV have no clear symptoms. RTSV can be transmitted by GLH from plants infected with RTSV alone, but RTBV cannot be transmitted from plants infected with RTBV alone.

We studied the natural occurrence and incidence of these viruses at IRRI in 1983 wet season when there was high RTV incidence. A leaf sample (second or third leaf from the youngest) that showed discoloration was collected from plants with typical RTV symptoms of stunting and leaf

Incidence of RTBV and RTSV on susceptible rice cultivars with and without RTV symptoms as detected by latex agglutination test.

Variety	With RTV symptoms					Without RTV symptoms				
	Leaves tested (no.)	RTBV+ RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	None	Leaves tested (no.)	RTBV+ RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	None
IR8	50	50	0	0	0	50	0	0	17	33
IR22	75	75	0	0	0	75	3	0	53	19
IR36	71	71	0	0	0	29	2	0	23	4
IR42	61	60	1	0	0	10	2	0	6	2
UPL-Ri 2	69	69	0	0	0	31	6	2	6	17
Total	326	325	1	0	0	195	13	2	105	75

yellowing. Samples also were collected from healthy looking plants in the same field. The virus or viruses in each sample were detected serologically using the latex test. Of 326 leaves from plants with RTV symptoms, 325 had both RTBV and RTSV and one had RTBV alone, indicating that susceptible plants with typical RTV symptoms usually were infected with both particles.

In contrast, 13 leaves from healthy looking plants had both RTBV and RTSV, 2 had RTBV alone, and 105 had RTSV. IR22 had the highest RTSV incidence and all varieties had plants infected with RTSV alone (see table).

Leaves from healthy looking plants that contained both particles might not have shown RTV symptoms at sampling although they were infected with both viruses. RTBV incidence was very low and the number of RTSV infected plants was unusually high. Generally, the number of RTSV-infected plants is very low when the virus source is infected with RTSV and RTBV in greenhouse tests. However, once RTSV is isolated, GLH can easily transmit it. High RTSV incidence in the field indicates that RTSV is spreading as an independent virus disease at the IRRI farm. This is the first report on natural RTSV occurrence outside Japan. □

Inhibitory effect of *Aspergillus terreus* Thom against *Rhizoctonia solani* f. sp. *sasakii*

A. K. Roy, Regional Research Station, Assam Agricultural University, Diphu 782460, Assam, India

In in vitro and pot tests, *A. terreus* isolated from soil inhibited growth of *R. solani* Kühn f. sp. *sasakii* Exner [= *Thanatephorus sasakii* (shirai) Tu and Kimbrough], the rice sheath blight (ShB) fungus.

Eight-mm-diameter holes were made near the edge of previously layered PDA (15 ml) in 10-cm petri dishes. *A. terreus* was grown in potato dextrose broth for 9 d at room temperature (16-26°C, av 21°C), and 0.15 ml of cold or boiled metabolic solution was poured into a hole for each treatment. In the 3d treatment, an 8-mm-diam mycelial disc of *A. terreus* replaced the metabolic solution. Plain potato dextrose broth was

used in the control treatment. A disc of *R. solani sasakii* was put in each petri dish and allowed to grow for 3 d. A 2.6 mm inhibitory zone developed in the 3d treatment (see figure).

In another test, a cold or boiled metabolic solution of *A. terreus* grown for 2 wk at 23 to 30°C (av 26.5°C) was mixed with PDA at 10% vol/vol. The medium was poured into petri dishes and a disc of *R. solani sasakii* was placed in the center. Treatment 3, above, was repeated. After 3 d, colony diameter was 59 mm for the treatment using the cold medium, 75 mm for the boiled solution, and 95 mm for the control.

In 20-cm-diam plastic pots with 2 kg sterilized soil, we inoculated 40 g of *A. terreus* and *R. solani sasakii* cultures grown on 3% maize-meal sand medium.

Inoculation was with *R. solani sasakii* alone, *A. terreus* alone, or *R. solani sasakii* + *A. terreus*. One-month-old seedlings of Pusa 2-21 were transplanted

Inhibitory effect of *A. terreus*: (from left) inhibitory zone against the colony of *R. solani sasakii*, reduced colony of *R. solani sasakii* in presence of cold extract of *A. terreus*, normal colony of *R. solani sasakii*.

into the plots and disease development was rated using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice. ShB incidence was less with *A. terreus*. ShB score was 4.4 with *R. solani sasakii* alone and 0.3 with both organisms. Inoculation with *A. terreus* alone did not affect plant growth. □